

JUSTIFICATION OF THE BLADE INSTALLATION ANGLE RELATIVE TO THE HORIZONTAL

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Annotation. The article analyzes the theoretical justification of the installation angle of flat-cutting blades relative to the horizontal for cultivators used in inter-row cultivation of cotton. Proper cultivation of cotton inter-rows improves soil aeration, moisture retention, microbiological activity, and eliminates weeds, which significantly affects crop productivity. The design parameters of the flat-cutting sweep, including blade length, working width, installation angle, and wing opening angle, were analyzed. A theoretical model describing the interaction between soil and the working body was developed based on the decomposition of forces acting on the blade into normal and tangential components. Analytical expressions were derived to determine the optimal blade installation angle that minimizes traction resistance and ensures efficient soil cutting. The results show that for compacted soils after irrigation, the optimal installation angle of the sweep blades relative to the horizontal should be within the range of 12°-20°.

Keywords: inter-row cultivation, cotton cultivator, flat cutting sweep, blade installation angle, soil-tool interaction, traction resistance

Introduction.

Cotton is one of the main agricultural crops cultivated in many countries of the world and plays an important role in the global textile industry. According to the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), the global cotton cultivation area exceeds 32 million hectares, with an annual production of more than 25 million tons of fiber. Uzbekistan is among the leading cotton-producing countries, where cotton is cultivated on approximately 1.0-1.1 million hectares of irrigated land, and it remains one of the strategically important crops of the national agricultural sector [1,2].

Efficient cultivation of cotton requires proper agrotechnical measures during the growing season. One of the most important technological operations is inter-row cultivation, which improves soil aeration, preserves soil moisture, activates microbiological processes, and eliminates weeds. Timely and high-quality inter-row cultivation can significantly improve plant growth and development conditions. On the contrary, improper soil cultivation may lead to soil moisture loss, root damage, delayed plant development by 10-15 days, and yield reduction by 6-8 centners per hectare [3].

Modern cotton cultivation technologies widely use cultivators equipped with different types of working bodies such as sweeps, knives, and loosening tools. The efficiency of these implements depends largely on their geometrical parameters and installation angles, which directly affect soil cutting conditions, traction resistance, soil crumbling quality, and weed removal efficiency. Therefore, the optimization of working body parameters is considered an important research direction in agricultural machinery engineering [4].

Several researchers have investigated the performance of cultivator sweeps and their interaction with soil. Hanna et al. studied mechanical weed control using cultivator sweeps and showed that the width and configuration of working bodies significantly influence weed removal efficiency and energy consumption [5]. Marakoglu and Carma analyzed the effect of working depth, speed, and sweep angle on draft force and soil disturbance during cultivation operations [6]. Hemeda investigated the soil-tool interaction process and developed mathematical models describing the forces acting on tillage tools [7]. However, despite numerous studies, the optimal installation angle of flat-cutting blades relative to the horizontal for cotton inter-row cultivation under irrigated soil conditions has not been sufficiently justified. In particular, soil compaction after irrigation significantly affects the cutting process, traction resistance, and soil crumbling quality. Therefore, determining the optimal geometric parameters of flat-cutting sweeps used in cotton cultivators remains an акрыal scientific and practical problem.

The purpose of this research is to theoretically substantiate the installation angle of flat-cutting blades relative to the horizontal, ensuring effective soil cutting, reduction of traction resistance, and improvement of inter-row cultivation quality in cotton fields.

Method.

The research was carried out using theoretical and analytical methods. The interaction between the flat-cutting sweep and soil was analyzed using the principles of soil mechanics and agricultural machinery theory. Forces acting on the blade were decomposed into normal and tangential components, and their relationship was expressed through analytical equations. The influence of friction coefficient and soil internal friction angle on the cutting process was considered. Based on energy optimization conditions, mathematical expressions were derived to determine the optimal installation angle of the blade relative to the horizontal.

Results and discussions.

Efficient use of irrigation water plays an important role in ensuring proper growth and development of cotton plants, and inter-row cultivation is one of the key agrotechnical operations in this process. Inter-row cultivation improves the soil water-physical and microbiological properties, enhances air exchange, optimizes the nutrient regime, and eliminates weeds. The cultivation of cotton inter-rows is carried out taking into account soil characteristics, field relief, and water supply conditions, while the working depth, number of operations, and timing of cultivation are determined accordingly.

If inter-row cultivation is not performed on time and with proper quality, it may lead to moisture loss in the soil, damage to plant roots, and slowing of plant growth and development. As a result, the vegetative period may be delayed by **10–15 days**, and crop yield may decrease by **6–8 centners per hectare** [8].

Fig. 1 shows the schematic diagram of a flat-cutting sweep designed for wide-coverage cotton cultivators.

1 – shank (stand); 2 – blade; a – blade length; L – shank height; B – working width; b – blade width; γ – blade opening angle; α – blade installation angle relative to the horizontal; β – blade crushing (pulverizing) angle; h – height of the blade tip above the horizontal.

Fig. 1. Structural scheme of the proposed flat-cutting sweep for a wide-coverage cotton cultivator

The proposed flat-cutting sweep has a **V-shaped design** and performs technological operations such as cutting weeds in cotton inter-rows, loosening the soil, and forming irrigation furrows during different stages of the vegetation period.

The angle α represents the installation angle of the blade relative to the horizontal. This parameter plays an important role in forming an optimal ratio of **normal and tangential forces** during the cutting of the soil layer. It also ensures that the cut weeds and soil mass slide along the blade surface and allows the soil to be loosened without bringing the lower moist soil layer to the surface.

Let the **total force acting on the blade be denoted by R**. This force can be decomposed into **tangential (traction) and normal components**:

$$R_x = R \cdot \cos(\alpha + \varphi), \quad R_y = R \cdot \sin(\alpha + \varphi), \quad (1)$$

where $\varphi = \arctan \mu$ – friction angle, grad;

μ – coefficient of friction.

Sliding condition (for the soil masses to move along the blade surface):

$$\alpha \geq \varphi + \Delta_\alpha, \quad (2)$$

In energy optimization, the power required for traction is expressed as:

$$P = v \cdot R_x = v \cdot R \cdot \cos(\alpha + \varphi), \quad (3)$$

However, the force RRR itself depends on the angle α ; for oblique cutting, the classical approximation is expressed as follows:

$$R(\alpha) = \frac{R_*}{\cos(\alpha - \varphi_i)}, \quad (4)$$

where R_* – the basic resistance, N; φ – the internal friction angle, degrees.

By combining expressions (2.3) and (2.4), we obtain:

$$P(\alpha) = v \cdot \frac{R_*}{\cos(\alpha - \varphi_i)} \cos(\alpha + \varphi), \quad (5)$$

The condition for the optimal angle is as follows:

$$\frac{dP}{d\alpha} = 0, \quad (6)$$

As a result, the lifting angle of the flat-cutting sweep wings relative to the horizontal can be expressed as follows:

$$\alpha \approx \varphi + \varphi_i, \quad (7)$$

Based on the literature sources [7], it was determined that under compacted soil conditions after irrigation, when the internal friction angle is $\varphi=22^\circ-28^\circ$, the lifting angle of the flat-cutting sweep wings relative to the horizontal should be within the range of $12^\circ-20^\circ$.

Conclusion

1. The conducted analysis showed that the installation angle of the flat-cutting sweep blade significantly influences soil cutting efficiency and traction resistance. When the angle is too small, soil crumbling decreases and traction resistance increases, while excessive angles may lead to unnecessary soil displacement and energy consumption.

Theoretical calculations indicate that under compacted soil conditions after irrigation, when the soil internal friction angle is within $22^\circ-28^\circ$, the optimal blade installation angle relative to the horizontal should be $12^\circ-20^\circ$. These parameters ensure effective weed cutting, proper soil loosening, and improved energy efficiency of the cultivator during cotton inter-row cultivation.

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